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Theoretical and Experimental Investigation of the Thermal Stability of a Cycloid Speed Reducer

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Abstract: High-precision drives are essential for ensuring accuracy and repeatability in positioning systems within robotics and industrial automation. Among these, cycloidal reducers are widely utilized due to their ability to deliver a high transmission ratio alongside high power density. However, compact designs often face challenges such as elevated operating temperatures caused by limited heat dissipation areas, making it crucial to assess thermal stability within the design process. While engineering practice typically determines the thermal stability of gear drives using ISO/TR 14179-2:2001, no specific methodologies have yet been developed for cycloidal reducers. To address this gap, this paper presents a novel mathematical model fine-tuned to quantify power dissipation and predict lubricant stabilization temperatures under varying operating conditions. The model employs a global energy balance approach, correlating total power losses with the heat dissipated from the reducer to the environment. Moreover, in this study, an experimental campaign was carried out to monitor the thermal behaviour of a cycloidal reducer under various operating conditions in terms of speed and transmitted torque. This was achieved through the analysis of images collected with an infrared thermal camera, both during the transient phase and under steady-state thermal conditions. The results demonstrate good alignment with experimental findings, although further refinements are required to develop specialized tools for cycloidal drives. Additional contributions of the present paper include the understanding of the time required to achieve thermal stability, as well as insights into heat generation and propagation. Beyond advancing scientific knowledge, this work also provides valuable practical guidance for engineering applications.

Keywords: cycloidal reducer; efficiency; power losses; thermal stability; lubricant stabilization temperature; experiments; infrared thermal imaging

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1. Introduction

Although planetary and harmonic reducers were almost irreplaceable high-precision reducers in the past, cycloidal reducers have been almost exclusively used in recent years. They are being increasingly developed nowadays and they have promising prospects in modern industry [1]. The importance of these power transmissions for Industry 4.0 is best illustrated in one of the recent reports on modern industry trends, which states that high-precision reducers account for 35% of the total costs of industrial robots because they

are found in almost all of their joints [2]. In addition to costs, precision, compactness, and efficiency, reliability plays a crucial role in the competitiveness of cycloidal reducers. Nonetheless, their competitiveness is limited in dynamic working conditions because they not only cause increased levels of noise and vibration but also lead to impaired thermal stability [3–6]. The most common problems associated with impaired thermal stability include decreased lubricant viscosity (decreased oil film thickness), increased wear and tear of the contact surfaces, shortening of the service life of the lubricant and the sealing elements, and appearance of thermal stresses [7–10]. In order to achieve thermal stability, it is necessary to stabilize the operating temperature, that is, to equalize the power loss inside the cycloidal reducer and convert it into heat with the amount of heat dissipated into the environment.

Over the past few years, the process of estimating power losses has advanced significantly. In several earlier works, e.g., [11–13], the values of friction coefficients were assumed to be constant in order to avoid taking complex tribological processes into account. However, the accuracy of such an approach is limited by a given range of operating conditions. In order to overcome these limitations, a group of researchers used a Thermal Elastohydrodynamic Lubrication (TEHL) model [14–16] and a numerical tool based on Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) [17,18] to estimate power losses. Here, friction and power losses are calculated directly depending on the working conditions, the roughness of the contact surfaces, and the characteristics of the lubricant. Although these methods are superior in terms of accuracy and applicability, their main disadvantage is that they require a long time for calculation.

Recently, a method for the prediction of temperature distribution on the key elements of the cycloidal reducer has drawn considerable attention. This is attributable to improved computer technology and numerical tools. The tools based on the Finite Element Method (FEA) are especially important because they provide information about the behaviour of the system in operational conditions while still in the product development stage. However, due to the complex kinematics of cycloidal reducers, current numerical investigations are limited. Furthermore, since significant simplifications are sometimes adopted, the reliability of this approach can be called into question. For example, Wei [19] et al. investigated the temperature distribution on one cycloidal disc tooth assuming that the transfer of load and heat are the same for all other cycloidal disc teeth. This is obviously not the case in reality since the distribution of contact forces is uneven. The research of Blagojevic et al. [20] provided much more realistic data on the temperature distribution of the key elements of the cycloidal reducer. According to this model, the highest contact temperature occurs inside the eccentric bearing because the highest intensities of the temperature sources are observed in that zone (power losses), that is, the contact forces are the strongest here.

According to Blok [21], the contact temperature between two elements consists of flash temperature and bulk temperature. The flash temperature refers to the temperature rise caused by current friction [22]. It is transient and lasts a very short time. The bulk temperature refers to the ambient temperature. In previous studies, the bulk temperature was generally taken as the lubricant temperature [23]. However, the bulk temperature is slightly higher than the lubricant temperature because the contact temperature first increases and then reaches a steady state due to the interaction with the lubricant. So far, researchers have made considerable efforts to define a model to assess the bulk temperature. The Thermal Network Method (TNM) has been used in many papers for different types of reducers including planetary reducers [24,25], reducers with cylindrical gears [26,27], and worm gear reducers [28]. Another common procedure for quantifying bulk temperature is defined by the international standard ISO/TR 14179-2:2001 [29]. However, this standard is mainly intended for cylindrical, bevel, and hypoid gears. To date, there has not been much

research conducted on the thermal conditions in cycloidal reducers. Zah [30] established a direct dependence between the increase in the lubricant temperature, ambient temperature, and power losses in stationary operating conditions (constant speed and constant torque). However, with this model, the heat is dissipated into the environment only through the flat surface of the housing, which is not the case in real operating conditions. In reality, the housing has a much more complex geometry, and a certain amount of the heat is dissipated through the foot mount.

For this reason, the main goal of this paper is to develop a mathematical model that can quantify power dissipation and predict the lubricant stabilization temperature for any combination of stationary operating conditions and thus assess the thermal stability of a cycloidal reducer. Indeed, the possibility of quantifying the thermal sources and predicting the lubricant stabilization temperature as a function of various input parameters makes it possible to find the best compromise solution for reaching the maximum bearing capacity of the reducer.

The developed method is crucial both for the current and future development of cycloidal reducers. It can be used in design processes in order to avoid expensive and time-consuming prototype testing. Moreover, while optimizing new conceptual solutions, the bearing capacity of a reducer can be regarded as a target function, while the lubricant stabilization temperature can be considered a limitation.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Contact Forces Distribution

During the transformation of the power and motion parameters of the reducer, a part of mechanical energy is lost and converted into thermal energy. In commonly used single-stage cycloidal reducers with two cycloidal discs, if mechanical losses ($\eta_{CR} \approx 1$) are neglected, the dependence between the torques is given as [31,32]:

$$T_{in} - 2T_2 + T_{out} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where T_{in} is the torque at the input shaft, $2T_2$ is the torque at the ring gear (ring gear rollers) coming from both cycloidal discs, and T_{out} is the torque at the output shaft.

If the torques acting only on one cycloidal disc are taken into account and mechanical losses are neglected, then the dependence between the torques can be written in the following form [31]:

$$T_1 - T_2 + T_3 = 0 \quad (2)$$

where T_1 is the driving torque of one cycloidal disc ($T_1 = T_{in}/2$), T_2 is the torque at the ring gear coming from one cycloidal disc, and T_3 is the output torque also coming from one cycloidal disc ($T_3 = T_{out}/2$).

As a result of the torques acting on the cycloidal disc components, three contact forces (reactions) appear, namely the following [31–34]:

- Contact force F_{Ni} on the current contact surface between the cycloidal disc teeth and the ring gear rollers (normal contact force).
- Contact force F_{Kj} on the current contact surface of the output rollers and the holes in the cycloidal disc (output contact force).
- Eccentric force F_E , which is considered to be a concentrated force acting in the centre of the cycloidal disc C_1 , forming the angle ε with the x -axis.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of these contact forces on one cycloidal disc at a drive angle of 0° . Since the same contact forces offset at 180° act on the other cycloidal disc, which is offset at 180° in relation to the first cycloidal disc, only one disc will be studied.

Figure 1. Distribution of contact forces on a cycloidal disc at the drive angle $\beta = 0^\circ$.

In this case, the influence of the clearances between the elements of the cycloidal reducer is not taken into account, so it is assumed that all the rollers (ring gear and output) come into contact with the cycloidal disc and that half of them participate in the transmission of the torque at any time. However, in real operating conditions, this is not the case because there are always clearances in order to overcome manufacturing errors, enable proper assembly and disassembly, ensure better lubrication, etc. The size of clearances directly affects the number of rollers that transmit the torque, and thus the distribution of contact forces. The larger the size of the clearances, the smaller the number of rollers carrying the load. In this paper, it is assumed that 2/3 of the ring gear and output rollers participate in the load transfer, i.e., 1/3 of the rollers per one cycloidal disc [31]. For this reason, 20% of the ring gear and output rollers per one cycloidal disc, which is the closest to the direction of eccentricity, are excluded from the load transfer process (the rollers whose centres lie on the direction of eccentricity do not transmit the torque).

The Lehmann model was chosen as the most suitable mathematical model for the calculation of the values of the normal F_{Ni} and output F_{Kj} contact forces. This model is described in detail in Reference [34] and only the basic expressions are shown here.

The values of the normal $F_{Ni}(\beta)$ and output $F_{Kj}(\beta)$ contact forces are calculated based on the following expressions:

$$F_{Ni}(\beta) = (c_N \cdot \Delta\beta) \cdot r_{Ni}(\beta) \cdot \sin \psi_{Ni}(\beta) \tag{3}$$

$$F_{Kj}(\beta) = (c_K \cdot \Delta\beta) \cdot r_{Kj}(\beta) \cdot \sin \psi_{Kj}(\beta) \tag{4}$$

where c_N and c_K are the stiffness of the ring gear and output rollers, $\Delta\beta$ is the small angular displacement of the cycloidal disc, $r_{Ni}(\beta)$ is the distance between the line of contact of the i -th ring gear roller and the central axis of the cycloidal disc, $\psi_{Ni}(\beta)$ is the angle between the direction of action of the normal contact forces of the i -th ring gear roller and the direction $r_{Ni}(\beta)$ that connects the line of contact and the central axis of the cycloidal disc, $r_{Kj}(\beta)$ is the distance between the line of contact of the j -th output roller and the central axis of the cycloidal disc, and $\psi_{Kj}(\beta)$ is the angle between the direction of action of the output contact

force $F_{K_j}(\beta)$ and the direction $r_{K_j}(\beta)$ that connects the contact line with the central axis of the cycloidal disc.

The total value of the eccentric force can be determined as the result of the horizontal $F_{EH}(\beta)$ and the vertical F_{EV} components [31,34,35]:

$$F_E(\beta) = \sqrt{F_{EH}(\beta)^2 + F_{EV}^2} \quad (5)$$

2.2. Calculation of Power Losses

In order to investigate the thermal stability of the cycloidal reducer, it is necessary to accurately determine power losses and efficiency. On the other hand, in order to calculate the efficiency, we need to know either the input power P_{in} and the output power P_{out} , or the input power P_{in} and the power losses P_L :

$$\eta_{CR} = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} = \frac{P_{in} - P_L}{P_{in}} < 1, \quad (6)$$

According to Linke [36] and Niemann and Winter [37], power losses in gear drives can be divided into load-dependant and load-independent losses (sub-index L_0). The former is directly proportional to the torque, while the latter does not depend on it. However, higher torques imply higher operating temperatures. At higher operating temperatures, lubricant properties (density and viscosity) change, which has a direct impact on the load-independent power losses. This primarily involves the power losses resulting from the interaction between the lubricant and the cycloidal disc P_{LG0} and from the interaction between the lubricant and the bearing elements P_{LB0} .

A further classification of power losses can be made according to the contacts between the mechanical components, as shown in Figure 2. These losses occur as a result of the friction between the cycloidal disc and the rollers (ring gear rollers P_{LG1} and output rollers P_{LG2}), the pins and the rollers (ring gear rollers P_{LP1} and output P_{LP2}), and the elements of the bearings P_{LB} (eccentric bearing, input, and output shaft bearings) and radial shaft seals P_{LS} .

Figure 2. Areas of mechanical power losses.

The total power losses in the cycloidal reducer P_L (load-dependent and load-independent) are calculated by summing up the individual losses, as shown in Figure 3. The following symbols are used: n_1 —the total number of cycloidal discs, n_2 —the total number of bearings, and n_3 —the total number of radial seals.

$$P_L = \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} (P_{LG1} + P_{LG2} + P_{LG0} + P_{LP1} + P_{LP2}) + \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} (P_{LB} + P_{LB0}) + \sum_{i=1}^{n_3} P_{LS}$$

Figure 3. Total power losses in a cycloidal reducer.

2.2.1. Power Losses in Cycloidal Gears

The load-dependent power losses in cycloidal gears occur between the cycloidal disc teeth and the ring gear rollers P_{LG1} , as well as between the circular holes in the cycloidal disc and the output rollers P_{LG2} . For their analysis, a mathematical model was developed based on the kinematic analysis of the meshing of cycloidal gears and the theory of contact mechanics.

Figure 4a shows the contact force F_{Ni} between the cycloidal disc teeth and the i -th ring gear roller, as well as the friction force F_{fgi} , which acts in the direction opposite to the direction of rotation of the roller. The direction of the contact force F_{Ni} is shifted from the centre of the rotation axis depending on the value of the rolling resistance coefficient f_{r1} . The shift in the direction of rolling occurs as a result of the difference between the mechanical work spent on elastic deformations on the front side of the contact and the mechanical work spent on elastic deformations on the rear side of the contact [38].

Figure 4. Kinematic analysis of the meshing of the cycloidal disc with: (a) ring gear rollers; (b) output rollers.

The power losses in this contact can be calculated as the product of the friction torque and the angular velocity of the ring gear rollers ω_2 :

$$P_{LG1} = \sum_{i=1}^p F_{Ni} \cdot \mu_{r1} \cdot \frac{D_0}{2} \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \omega_2 \tag{7}$$

where p is the current number of the ring gear rollers that are in contact with the cycloidal disc teeth and transfer the load, D_0 is the diameter of the ring gear rollers, and μ_{r1} is the coefficient of rolling friction between the ring gear rollers and the cycloidal disc teeth.

In the literature, μ_{r1} is very often defined as $\mu_{r1} = f_{r1}/0.5D_0$, where f_{r1} is the rolling resistance coefficient. These two coefficients differ from each other. The first one is dimensionless, while the second one has a length.

The angular velocity of the ring gear rollers can be calculated as $\omega_2 = \omega_{in}/(z_1 + 1)$, where ω_{in} is the angular velocity of the input shaft and z_1 is the number of cycloidal disc teeth.

Figure 4b shows the contact force F_{Kj} between the holes in the cycloidal disc and the j -th output roller, as well as the friction force F_{fgj} . The contact direction of the contact force F_{Kj} is shifted from the centre of the rotation axis in the direction of rolling of the roller depending on the value of the rolling resistance coefficient f_{r2} . The power losses in this contact can be calculated based on the following expression:

$$P_{LG2} = \sum_{j=1}^q F_{Kj} \cdot \mu_{r2} \cdot \frac{D_{VK}}{2} \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \omega_4 \quad (8)$$

where q is the current number of the output rollers that are in contact with the holes on the cycloidal disc and transfer the load, D_{VK} is the diameter of the output rollers, μ_{r2} is the coefficient of the rolling friction between the output rollers and the holes on the cycloidal disc, and ω_4 is the angular velocity of the output rollers.

In general, power losses due to the interaction between the elements and the lubricant can be divided into churning, windage, and squeezing losses. In cycloidal reducers, the squeezing losses are predominant, while the churning losses are less pronounced [17].

Determining squeezing losses is one of the unsolvable problems, both in engineering practice and science, because it involves studying streamlines going through a complex geometric space. This is a chaotic flow that generally leads to the formation of a vortex flow with irregular, time-varying, and mixed streamlines. A group of researchers tried to overcome these limitations using numerical methods (CFD) [17] to estimate power losses. However, numerical research methods generally lack experimental verification.

Churning losses occur in conditions of partial immersion, i.e., when the lubricant is splashed around into the free space [9]. They can be assessed by empirical mathematical models proposed by Mauz [39] and Changenet [40] or by numerical methods such as CFD analysis [17]. Since lubricant flow is a very complex phenomenon, mathematical models are applicable only in a limited range of operating conditions and are mainly valid for involute gears. Numerical simulations yield much more reliable results because they directly take into account complex hydrodynamic processes. Although these methods are superior in terms of accuracy and applicability, their main disadvantage is that they require a long time for calculation. Therefore, in this paper, churning losses were calculated approximately using the Changenet mathematical model adapted to cycloidal reducers by analogy as follows:

$$P_{LG0} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot \omega_3^3 \cdot R_b^3 \cdot S_m \cdot C_m \quad (9)$$

where ρ is the lubricant density, ω_3 is the angular speed of the cycloidal disc ($\omega_3 = \omega_{out}$), S_p is the immersed area of the cycloidal disc, R_b is the radius of the base circle of the cycloidal disc, and C_m is the dimensionless coefficient of the friction torque that depends on the flow regime during the interaction of the cycloidal disc with the lubricant.

2.2.2. Power Losses in Pins

In classical cycloidal reducers, the ring gear rollers and the output rollers are installed directly on the pins, so the sliding friction that occurs in this contact leads to power losses P_{LP1} and P_{LP2} . Further in the text, a mathematical model used to assess these losses will be presented.

Figure 4a shows the contact force F_{Ni} , which causes the load on the pin through the i -th ring gear roller. Their contact is theoretically realized along a line, but with the appearance of contact deformations, the lines turn into contact zones. Between these contact zones, the friction force F_{fpi} acts in the opposite direction to the direction of the rotation of the roller. The power losses can be calculated as the product of the friction torque and the angular velocity of the ring gear rollers ω_2 as follows:

$$P_{LP1} = \sum_{i=1}^p F_{Ni} \cdot \mu_{s1} \cdot \frac{d_0}{2} \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \omega_2 \quad (10)$$

where μ_{s1} is the sliding friction coefficient between the ring gear rollers and their pins, and d_0 is the diameter of the ring gear pin.

The same method was used for the expressions for the calculation of the power losses between the output rollers and their pins. Figure 4b shows the friction force F_{fpj} and the contact force F_{Kj} , which causes the load on the pin through the j -th output roller. The power losses in this contact can be calculated as follows:

$$P_{LP2} = \sum_{j=1}^q F_{Kj} \cdot \mu_{s2} \cdot \frac{d_{VK}}{2} \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \omega_4 \quad (11)$$

where μ_{s2} is the sliding friction coefficient between the output rollers and their pins, and d_{VK} is the diameter of the output pin.

2.2.3. Power Losses in Bearings

The power losses in bearings consist of load-dependent power losses P_{LB} and load-independent power losses P_{LB0} . Different empirical mathematical models, commercial software developed by bearing manufacturers (SKF, Schaeffler) [41,42], and numerical methods, such as CFD analysis [18], can all be used for their evaluation. Due to its simplicity and the fact that it gives good results, Schaeffler's empirical mathematical model has found the widest application [43]. This model requires knowledge of the bearing geometry, load, angular velocity, operating temperature, lubrication method, and type of lubricant. The power losses in bearings are calculated as follows:

$$P_{LB} = f_1 \cdot F \cdot d_m \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \omega \quad (12)$$

$$P_{LB0} = 10^{-10} \cdot f_0 \cdot (v_{lub} \cdot n)^{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot d_m^3 \cdot \omega \quad (13)$$

where f_1 is a factor that depends on the type of the bearing and the direction of the load, f_0 is a coefficient that depends on the type of the bearing and the lubrication method, F is the bearing load, d_m is the mean diameter of the bearing, v_{lub} is the kinematic viscosity of the lubricant at the operating temperature, n is the speed of the bearing, and ω is the angular velocity of the bearing.

These power losses are calculated for each bearing separately. In the eccentric bearing, the absolute angular velocity is determined as $(\omega_{in} + \omega_{out})$ because the input shaft rotates in the opposite direction to the output shaft.

2.2.4. Power Losses in Seals

The power losses in the contacts between the radial seals and the shafts depend on various factors such as the material of the seal, the roughness of the shaft surface in the area of the sealing lips, the lubricant used, and the temperature of the sealing area. Since manufacturers' catalogues contain all the necessary information, they can be used for their

assessment. Nonetheless, due to its simplicity, the following empirical expression from the ISO/TR 14179-2 [29] standard is generally used:

$$P_{LS} = 7.69 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot d_{sh}^2 \cdot n_{sh} \quad (14)$$

where d_{sh} is the shaft diameter and n_{sh} is the shaft speed.

2.3. Thermal Model

A mathematical model was developed based on the global energy balance between the total power losses P_L converted into heat and the total amount of heat \dot{Q} dissipated from the inside of the cycloidal reducer into the environment in order to predict the lubricant stabilization temperature at a certain load and the maximum load at a desired lubricant stabilization temperature.

According to the international standard ISO/TR 14179-2 [29], the total amount of dissipated heat can be divided into the heat dissipated through the housing \dot{Q}_{ho} , the heat dissipated through the external parts of the shaft \dot{Q}_{sh} , and the heat dissipated through the couplings \dot{Q}_{co} .

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{Q}_{ho} + \sum_{i=1} \dot{Q}_{sh} + \sum_{i=1} \dot{Q}_{co} \quad (15)$$

The ability of a mechanical component to dissipate heat can be estimated using the following basic heat transfer theory expression:

$$\dot{Q} = \frac{\Delta\theta}{R_{th}} \quad (16)$$

where $\Delta\theta$ is a temperature difference between the component and the fluid, and R_{th} is the thermal resistance.

2.3.1. Thermal Model for the Housing

Since the housing of a cycloidal reducer is generally made by casting, it usually has a very complex structure. However, in order to develop a general model for a larger number of housing types and to avoid a lengthy modelling process, it is considered to be a set of simple geometric elements (a set of vertical plates and cylindrical rings), while the geometry with a negligible impact on the thermal calculation (radii, openings, etc.) is not taken into account. The foot mount is modelled as an assembly of rectangular fins with one-dimensional heat dissipation and is accounted for through the use of an extended surface. In this way, the total thermal resistance during heat dissipation through the housing represents the sum of thermal resistances for simple geometric elements as follows:

$$\frac{1}{R_{ho}} = \sum_{i=1} \frac{1}{R_{fw}} + \sum_{i=1} \frac{1}{R_{cw}} + \sum_{i=1} \frac{1}{R_{fn}} \quad (17)$$

where R_{fw} is the thermal resistance during heat dissipation through a vertical wall, R_{cw} is the thermal resistance during heat dissipation through the cylindrical wall, and R_{fn} is the thermal resistance through a rectangular extended surface (foot mount).

Modelling of the internal heat transfer (e.g., conductive transfer between the cycloidal disc and the rollers, convective transfer between the cycloidal disc and the lubricant, etc.) adds to the complexity of the approach and prolongs the calculation time while having a rather small impact on the global energy balance, hence the internal heat transfer is not taken into account. Instead, the lubricant stabilization temperature θ_{lub} is considered the mean temperature of the internal components of the transmission. Thus, the vertical and cylindrical walls of the housing are exposed to the stable lubricant temperature θ_{lub} from the

inside and the ambient temperature θ_{amb} from the outside. Therefore, the total temperature difference is $\Delta\theta = \theta_{lub} - \theta_{amb}$. These two temperatures are connected by thermal resistances that take into account conductive, convective, and radiative heat transfer. Figure 5 shows the thermal model of the cycloidal reducer.

Figure 5. Thermal model of the cycloidal reducer.

The thermal resistance during heat dissipation through the vertical wall R_{fw} is determined as follows:

$$R_{fw} = \frac{1}{\alpha_{lub} \cdot A_{wi,f}} + \frac{\delta_w}{\lambda_w \cdot A_{we,f}} + \frac{1}{(\alpha_{amb,fcon} + \alpha_{amb,rad}) \cdot A_{wo,f}} \quad (18)$$

where α_{lub} is the coefficient of heat transfer between the inner wall of the housing and the lubricant, $\alpha_{amb,fcon}$ is the convective heat transfer coefficient between the outer vertical wall of the housing and the environment, $\alpha_{amb,rad}$ is the coefficient of radiation heat transfer between the outer wall of the housing and the environment, δ_w is the thickness of the vertical wall of the housing, λ_w is the coefficient of thermal conductivity of the housing material, $A_{wi,f}$ is the inner surface area of the vertical wall of the housing, $A_{wo,f}$ is the outer surface area of the vertical wall of the housing, and $A_{we,f}$ is the equivalent surface area of the vertical housing wall, $A_{we,f} = (A_{wi,f} + A_{wo,f})/2$.

The thermal resistance during heat dissipation through the cylindrical wall R_{cw} is determined according to the following expression:

$$R_{cw} = \frac{1}{2\pi \cdot r_{wi} \cdot \alpha_{lub} \cdot L_c} + \frac{\ln(r_{wo}/r_{wi})}{2\pi \cdot \lambda_w \cdot L_c} + \frac{1}{2\pi \cdot r_{wo} \cdot (\alpha_{amb,ccon} + \alpha_{amb,rad}) \cdot L_c} \quad (19)$$

where $\alpha_{amb,ccon}$ is the coefficient of heat transfer by convection between the outer cylindrical wall of the housing and the environment, r_{wi} is the inner radius of the cylindrical wall of

the housing, r_{wo} is the outer radius of the cylindrical wall of the housing, and L_c is the length of the cylindrical wall of the housing.

The thermal resistance during heat dissipation through the cylindrical wall at the position of the rectangular fin R_{fn} is determined according to the following expressions:

- Transverse fin:

$$R_{fn} = \frac{1}{2\pi \cdot r_{wi} \cdot \alpha_{lub} \cdot \delta_f} + \frac{\ln(r_{wo}/r_{wi})}{2\pi \cdot \lambda_w \cdot \delta_f} + \frac{1}{\eta_f \cdot A_f \cdot (\alpha_{amb, fcon} + \alpha_{rad})} \quad (20)$$

- Longitudinal fin:

$$R_{fn} = \frac{1}{2\pi \cdot r_{wi} \cdot \alpha_{lub} \cdot L_f} + \frac{\ln(r_{wo}/r_{wi})}{2\pi \cdot \lambda_w \cdot L_f} + \frac{1}{\eta_f \cdot A_f \cdot (\alpha_{amb, fcon} + \alpha_{rad})} \quad (21)$$

where δ_f is the thickness of the rectangular fin, L_f is the length of the rectangular fin, η_f is the thermal efficiency of the rectangular fin, and A_f is the surface area of the rectangular fin.

The following expressions were used to determine these heat transfer coefficients:

- The free convective heat transfer between the outer vertical wall and the environment [44] is as follows:

$$\alpha_{amb, fcon} = \frac{N_u \cdot \lambda_{amb}}{L} = 0.28 \cdot \frac{\lambda_{amb}}{L} \cdot (G_{rL} \cdot P_r)^{0.3} \quad (22)$$

where N_u is the Nusselt number, P_r is the Prandtl number $P_r = (c_{p, amb} \cdot \mu_{amb}) / \lambda_{amb}$, G_{rL} is the Grashof number $G_{rL} = (g \cdot \beta \cdot (\theta_{lub} - \theta_{amb}) \cdot L^3) / \nu_{amb}^2$, L is the height of the vertical wall, g is the acceleration gravity, and β is the volume expansion coefficient. The environmental parameters include the heat conduction coefficient λ_{amb} , kinematic viscosity ν_{amb} , and the specific heat capacity at constant pressure $c_{p, amb}$. It is important to note that for inclined plates (as in the case of the longitudinal fin of the foot mount), the expression (22) can be applied up to an inclination angle of 45° , but $G_r \cdot P_r$ must be replaced by $G_r \cdot P_r \cdot \cos \varphi$, where φ is the angle of inclination of the plate in relation to the vertical plane [45].

- The free convective heat transfer between the outer cylindrical wall and the environment [46] is as follows:

$$\alpha_{amb, ccon} = \begin{cases} 0.53 \cdot \frac{\lambda_{amb}}{D_{ou}} \cdot (G_{rD} \cdot P_r)^{0.25}, & 10^4 < (G_{rD} \cdot P_r) < 10^9 \\ 0.114 \cdot \frac{\lambda_{amb}}{D_{ou}} \cdot (G_{rD} \cdot P_r)^{0.33}, & 10^9 < (G_{rD} \cdot P_r) < 10^{12} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

where G_{rD} is the Grashof number $G_{rD} = (g \cdot \beta \cdot (\theta_{lub} - \theta_{amb}) \cdot D_{ou}^3) / \nu_{amb}^2$ and D_{ou} is the outer diameter of the cylindrical wall.

- The radiative heat transfer between the outer wall and the environment [47] is as follows:

$$\alpha_{amb, rad} \approx 0.23 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \varepsilon \cdot \left(\frac{546.3 + \theta_{lub} + \theta_{amb}}{2} \right)^3 \quad (24)$$

where ε is the emissivity coefficient. For surfaces covered with protective coatings and paint, the value of the emissivity coefficient is within the limits of $0.90 \div 0.95$.

The coefficient of heat transfer between the inner wall of the housing and the lubricant α_{lub} is very hard to estimate mathematically. According to Funck [47], its value ranges from 150 to 300 $W/(m^2 \cdot K)$ and depends on the type of boundary layer that develops along the

inner wall of the housing (laminar, turbulent, or transitional boundary layers). However, for practical calculations, the value of $200 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K})$ is generally adopted.

The thermal efficiency of a rectangular fin is determined using the following expression:

$$\eta_f = \frac{\tanh(m_f \cdot L_f)}{m_f \cdot L_f} \quad (25)$$

where $m_f \cdot L_f$ is determined as follows:

$$m_f \cdot L_f = \sqrt{2 \cdot \frac{\alpha_{amb, fcon} + \alpha_{amb, rad}}{\delta_f \cdot \lambda_f}} \cdot L_f \quad (26)$$

2.3.2. Thermal Model for the Shafts and Couplings

In general, the outer parts of the shafts and couplings have relatively small surface areas, yet some heat is dissipated into the environment through them. In order to quantify their impact on the global energy balance, they are modelled as assemblies of two cylindrical rods of limited lengths, while the variable cross-sections are reduced to constant ones (Figure 5). Since the fluid of constant temperature θ_{amb} flows around the rods, there is heat exchange by convection. The rod that simulates the shaft is connected to the wall of the housing with its base. The temperature of the base $\theta_{saf, x=0}$ is assumed to be approximately equal to the lubricant stabilization temperature θ_{lub} , and for this reason the following can be written:

$$(\theta_{saf} - \theta_{amb})_{x=0} = (\theta_{lub} - \theta_{amb}) \quad (27)$$

Since the temperature on the side surface area of the rod is not the same everywhere, its value at the end of the rod is determined by integrating the differential equation, which describes the temperature change along the length of the rod. Here, the following is assumed:

$$(\theta_{cou} - \theta_{amb})_{x=l_s} = (\theta_{saf} - \theta_{amb})_{x=l_s} \quad (28)$$

This simplification was introduced by Funck [47]. By replacing the obtained integration constants and using simple algebraic transformations, we obtain the following:

$$(\theta_{saf} - \theta_{amb})_{x=l_s} = \frac{(\theta_{lub} - \theta_{amb})}{\cosh(m_{sh} \cdot l_{sh}) + \frac{\alpha_{sc}}{\lambda_{sh} \cdot m_{sh}} \cdot \sinh(m_{sh} \cdot l_{sh})} \quad (29)$$

where λ_{sh} is the thermal conductivity coefficient of the shaft material, m_{sh} is the dimensionless coefficient of the shaft rod, and α_{sc} is the coefficient of thermal conductivity between the shaft rod and the coupling rod in the transverse direction.

The thermal resistance during the heat dissipation through the outer part of the shaft R_{sh} is determined with the assumption that the front surface of the shaft transfers heat, hence:

$$R_{sh} = \frac{1}{\lambda_{sh} \cdot m_{sh} \cdot A_{sh} \cdot \frac{\frac{\alpha_{sc}}{\lambda_{sh} \cdot m_{sh}} + \tanh(m_{sh} \cdot l_{sh})}{1 + \frac{\alpha_{sc}}{\lambda_{sh} \cdot m_{sh}} \cdot \tanh(m_{sh} \cdot l_{sh})}} \quad (30)$$

where A_{sh} is the cross-sectional area of the shaft rod.

The thermal resistance during heat dissipation through the connected coupling R_{co} is determined on the assumption that the heat transfer through the front surface of the coupling is negligibly small, which results in the following expression:

$$R_{co} = \frac{1}{\frac{\lambda_{co} \cdot m_{co} \cdot A_{co} \cdot \tanh(m_{co} \cdot l_{co})}{\cosh(m_{sh} \cdot l_{sh}) + \frac{\alpha_{sc}}{\lambda_{sh} \cdot m_{sh}} \cdot \sinh(m_{sh} \cdot l_{sh})}} \quad (31)$$

where λ_{co} is the thermal conductivity coefficient of the coupling material, m_{co} is the dimensionless coefficient of the coupling rod, and A_{co} is the cross-sectional area of the coupling rod.

The dimensionless coefficients m_{sh} and m_{co} , which represent the ratio of the intensity of heat transfer from the side surface of the rod and the intensity of heat conduction along the rod, are determined using the following expressions:

$$m_{sh} = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_{sh} \cdot P_{sh}}{\lambda_{sh} \cdot A_{sh}}} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_{sh}}{\lambda_{sh} \cdot d_{sh}}} \quad (32)$$

$$m_{co} = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_{co} \cdot P_{co}}{\lambda_{co} \cdot A_{co}}} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_{co}}{\lambda_{co} \cdot d_{co}}} \quad (33)$$

where α_{sh} is the heat transfer coefficient between the side surface of the rod and the environment, α_{co} is the heat transfer coefficient between the side surface of the coupling and the environment, P_{sh} is the cross-sectional circumference of the shaft rod, and P_{co} is the cross-sectional circumference of the coupling rod.

The heat transfer coefficient between the shaft rod and the coupling rod in the transverse direction is determined by means of the following expression [36]:

$$\alpha_{sc} = \frac{\lambda_{co} \cdot m_{co} \cdot A_{co} \cdot \tanh(m_{co} \cdot l_{co})}{A_{sh}} \quad (34)$$

Becker's expressions for rotating cylinders [48] can be used to determine the heat transfer coefficients α_{sh} and α_{co} as follows:

$$\alpha_{sh} = 0.133 \cdot \frac{\lambda_{amb}}{d_{sh}} \cdot Re^{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (35)$$

$$\alpha_{co} = 0.133 \cdot \frac{\lambda_{amb}}{d_{co}} \cdot Re^{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (36)$$

where Re is the Reynolds number $Re = (\omega_i \cdot d_i^2) / (2 \cdot \nu_{amb})$, ω_i is the angular velocity of the shaft or the coupling rod, and d_i is the diameter of the shaft or the coupling rod.

2.3.3. Thermal Model for the Stable Lubricant Temperature

If the power losses are expressed through the input power P_{in} and the efficiency η_{CR} , then the equation of the global energy balance can be written in the following form:

$$P_{in} \cdot (1 - \eta_{CR}) = \dot{Q} \quad (37)$$

By replacing (15) and (16) in (37), we obtain the following basic equation for thermal calculation:

$$P_{in} \cdot (1 - \eta_{CR}) = \frac{\Delta\theta}{R_{ho}} + \sum_{i=1} \frac{\Delta\theta}{R_{sh}} + \sum_{i=1} \frac{\Delta\theta}{R_{co}} \quad (38)$$

Since the temperature difference $\Delta\theta$ for the given thermal resistances always represents the difference between the lubricant stabilization temperature and the ambient temperature ($\theta_{lub} - \theta_{amb}$), the lubricant stabilization temperature θ_{lub} can be determined as follows:

$$\theta_{lub} = \frac{P_{in} \cdot (1 - \eta_{CR})}{\frac{1}{R_{ho}} + \sum_{i=1} \frac{1}{R_{sh}} + \sum_{i=1} \frac{1}{R_{co}}} + \theta_{amb} \quad (39)$$

2.4. Model Validation

In order to confirm the validity of the presented mathematical models for assessment of the total power losses and the lubricant stabilization temperature, experimental tests were performed. One group of tests included changing of the input shaft speed at a constant load on the output shaft, while the other group of tests was based on the change in the load on the output shaft at a constant input speed.

The tests were carried out on a test bench shown in Figure 6. It consists of a driving Brushless DC motor (BLDC) (Ningbo Volcano Electric, Ningbo, China) and a magnetic brake (Chain Tail, Taichung City, Taiwan) that enables a controlled load from 20 to 200 N·m. The nominal power of the drive motor is 2 kW, and the nominal speed is 2500 min⁻¹. The operating speed of the drive motor is adjusted using a potentiometer, and the torque is calculated based on the measurements of the phase current, with the torque constant of the motor being known. A direct current at the interval of 0.53–0.79 A is used to control the braking torque, whereby each value of the direct current corresponds to a specific value of the braking torque.

Figure 6. Test bench: (1) BLDC motor; (2) shaft coupling; (3) input intermediate shaft; (4) cycloidal reducer; (5) output intermediate shaft; (6) shaft coupling; (7) magnetic powder brake; and (8) thermocouple.

The drive motor and the magnetic brake are connected to the cycloidal reducer (Sumitomo, Düsseldorf, Germany) by an intermediate shaft and claw couplings. It is a classical single-stage cycloidal reducer with a nominal power of 370 W and a transmission ratio of 15. The permissible load of the reducer at 1450 min⁻¹ is 32.5 N·m. Other characteristics of this cycloidal reducer are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Geometric characteristics of the studied cycloidal reducer.

Parameter	Units	Value
Transmission ratio, u_{CR}	-	15
Eccentricity, e	mm	1.6
Ring gear roller diameter, D_0	mm	8
Diameter of the housing roller pin, d_0	mm	6
Output roller diameter, D_{VK}	mm	8
Diameter of the output roller pin, d_{VK}	mm	6
Number of output rollers, u	-	8
Pitch circle diameter of output rollers, R_{0iz}	mm	26.2
Equivalent thickness of the walls of the housing, δ_w	mm	5

Table 2. Bearing specifications.

Position	Eccentric	Bearing A	Bearing B	Bearing C	Bearing D	Oil Seals (mm)
Input shaft				6301	6301Z	17 × 30 × 6
Output shaft		6204Z	6909			30 × 47 × 8
Cycloidal disc	607-YSX					

Unirex N2 grease (ExxonMobil, Houston, TX, USA) was used for lubrication of the cycloidal reducer. Its basic characteristics are shown in Table 3. The lubricant volume is approximately 0.025 L.

Table 3. Main characteristics of the lubricant.

Name	Thickener Type	Grade	Dropping Point, (°C)	Base Oil Viscosity, (mm^2/s)		Viscosity Index
				ν (40 °C)	ν (100 °C)	
Unirex N2	Lithium Complex	NLGI 2	210	115	12.2	95

The lubricant temperature was measured using a K-type thermocouple (Sterling Sensors, Oldham, England, UK). The thermocouple was mounted on the housing cover previously rotated by 120°. It was positioned this way so that the existing opening could be used for filling the lubricant.

The excitation voltage, which occurs as a result of the change in the lubricant temperature, was read using a special NI cDAQ-9178 (National Instruments, Austin, TX, USA) measuring station and the SignalExpress software 2015.

The surface temperature of the housing was also monitored using an infrared camera (DJI Technology, Nanshan, China) installed in front of the test bench.

In order to obtain comparable results, the ambient temperature was approximately the same for all the tests ($\theta_{amb} = 25 \text{ °C} \pm 1 \text{ °C}$). The duration of a single test was experimentally set to 240 min. This longer time period was required for the reducer to reach a stable operating temperature.

3. Results

This chapter gives a comparative analysis of the results obtained by analytical and experimental methods. The basic parameters used for the mathematical models are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Values of basic calculation parameters.

Parameter	Units	Value
Ambient temperature, θ_{amb}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25
Coefficient of rolling friction, μ_{r1}, μ_{r2}	-	0.003
Coefficient of sliding friction, μ_{s1}, μ_{s2}	-	0.03
Heat transfer coefficient for lubricant, α_{lub}	$\text{W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K})$	200
Thermal conductivity coefficient of the housing wall, λ_w	$\text{W}/(\text{m} \cdot \text{K})$	50
Emissivity coefficient, ε	-	0.90

3.1. Power Losses and Efficiency

Dependence of the efficiency and the total power losses on the input speed $n_{in} = (580; 780; 980; 1200; 1450) \text{ min}^{-1}$ is shown in Figure 7. The tests were performed for three independent stationary loads $T_{out} = (20; 26; 32) \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$. The efficiency has the lowest value of 0.88 when the torque is minimum and the input speed is maximum. An increase in the load at the same speed leads to an increase in the efficiency. Taking reasonable deviation into account, the analytical results show a good agreement with the experimental results. The average deviation for the efficiency values is 1.46% (max. 2.11%), while the average deviation for the power losses is 9.88% (max. 23.52%). It should be pointed out that the measurement results represent the mean values of experimentally determined efficiency values during the last 60 min of testing. The standard deviation estimated on the data set did not exceed 0.5% of the calculated mean values.

Figure 7. Comparison of analytically and experimentally obtained results of the efficiency and power losses at loads of (a) 20 N·m, (b) 26 N·m, and (c) 32 N·m.

The accuracy of the obtained results largely depends on the values of friction coefficients, which are not constant during the entire work of the cycloidal reducer. According to Stribeck, the friction between the contacting surfaces is a function of the relative thickness of the oil film and the lubrication regime. The relative thickness of the oil film is the ratio of the film thickness to the surface roughness. The greater the film thickness, the less likely that contact as a result of the surface roughness will occur. It is rather difficult to determine whether the internal elements of the cycloidal reducer operate under the mixed or hydrodynamic lubrication regime. Under hydrodynamic lubrication conditions, a change in viscosity caused by a change in the temperature and pressure will certainly bring about a transition to the mixed lubrication regime. At this point, the losses caused by the interaction between the elements and the lubricant are reduced. Since the recommended viscosity index for this type of reducers is 95, it is unlikely for the components to be under boundary lubrication conditions, except perhaps during the start-up phase.

3.2. Lubricant Stabilization Temperature

The dependence of the lubricant stabilization temperature on the input speed $n_{in} = (580; 780; 980; 1200; 1450) \text{ min}^{-1}$ is shown in Figure 8. The tests were performed for three independent stationary loads $T_{out} = (20; 26; 32) \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$. Experimentally measured temperatures were used to estimate the coefficients of heat transfer between the outer wall of the housing and the environment $\alpha_{amb,fcon}$, $\alpha_{amb,ccon}$, and $\alpha_{amb,rad}$. The stabilization temperature has the lowest value in the first case where the input speed is minimum. When the speed increases at the same load, the lubricant stabilization temperature increases. Therefore, the higher the power losses, the higher the operating stabilization temperature. Taking reasonable deviation into account, the analytical results show a good agreement with the experimentally measured values. The average deviation of the obtained results for the lubricant stabilization temperature is 7.54% (max. 14.3%). It should be also pointed out that the measurement results represent the mean values of experimentally measured lubricant temperatures during the last 60 min of the testing. The standard deviation estimated on the data set did not exceed 0.3% of the calculated mean values.

Figure 8. Comparison of analytical and experimental results for the lubricant stabilization temperature at loads of (a) 20 N·m, (b) 26 N·m, and (c) 32 N·m.

Figure 9 shows the heating of the lubricant at a nominal stationary load of 32 N·m. As the power that is lost inside the cycloidal reducer and converted into heat tends to equalize with the amount of heat dissipated into the environment, the value of the lubricant temperature increases until thermal stability is reached.

Figure 9. Heating of the lubricant until the thermal stability is reached.

The increase in the temperature is the largest in the first 30 min of operation, and then it becomes significantly lower. Although the obtained heating curve is not comparable to the mathematical model, it provides valuable insight into the time period needed to achieve thermal stability. It is important to note that a difference in the initial temperature of ± 1 °C is the result of multiple tests and incomplete cooling of the reducer after each test.

3.3. Thermal Imaging Analysis

The obtained series of infrared thermal (IRT) images at different constant speeds and constant loads help us understand the generation and propagation of heat both on the surface of the housing and in general. The only disadvantage of this method is that only the surface temperature of the housing can be monitored, while the internal temperature distribution on the key elements of the cycloidal reducer cannot be recorded.

Although a large number of images were obtained, only a few IRT images taken during a 240 min testing at an input speed of 1450 min^{-1} and a torque of 32 N·m are shown here (Figure 10). The initial surface temperature of the housing was between 24 °C and 25 °C, as was the initial ambient temperature. In the first minute, the highest surface temperature of the housing was 27.9 °C, in the third minute it was 29.3 °C, and in the last minute of the test it reached 48.1 °C.

Figure 10. IRT images taken during a 240 min testing at $n_{in} = 1450 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $T_{out} = 32 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$.

If we analyse the temperature fields, we can easily see that the highest temperature is in the area of the input shaft bearing and that it increases and moves towards the output shaft. The authors are of the opinion that such a distribution is the result of the proximity of the eccentric bearing, which is the biggest thermal source in the cycloidal reducer. The temperature distribution in the thermally stable cycloidal reducer is shown in the last picture.

4. Conclusions

This paper presents a mathematical model that can quantify power dissipation and predict the lubricant stabilization temperature in a single-stage cycloidal reducer for any combination of stationary operating conditions.

A comparative analysis of the analytical and experimental results shows that the average deviation of the obtained values for the lubricant stabilization temperature is 7.54%

(max. 14.3%). The character of the change in the stabilization temperature is the same for both the analytical and experimental results: an increase in the input speed at the same load and an increase in the load at the same speed cause an increase in the lubricant stabilization temperature. It must be pointed out that the accuracy of the thermal model is limited by previous calculations of the contact forces and efficiency, as well as by assumptions and simplifications defined during the modelling of heat transfer mechanisms.

The average deviation for the efficiency values is 1.46% (max. 2.11%), while the average deviation of the obtained values for the power losses is 9.88% (max. 23.52%). The character of the change in the efficiency is also the same for both the analytical and experimental results: an increase in the load at the same speed brings about an increase in the efficiency, while an increase in the input speed at the same load decreases the efficiency. The main sources of the power losses (thermal sources) are the losses between the rollers and the pins and the losses in the eccentric bearing.

The obtained values of the contact forces could not be verified experimentally. However, based on the obtained efficiency values, it can be assumed that they were well calculated.

As part of future research, it would be interesting to develop a thermal network that calculates the bulk temperatures of the key elements of a cycloidal reducer. It would also be interesting to investigate the lubricant temperature for transient operating conditions. Moreover, in this study, only one model of cycloidal reducer was analysed, limiting the exploration of configurations. To address this limitation, future studies should focus on varying the reducer parameters using a structured Design of Experiment (DoE) approach. Such investigations would enable the development of more refined and specific models tailored to the unique characteristics of cycloidal reducers, further enhancing their applicability and performance prediction.

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